

Coexistence of imipenemase (IMP) and verona integron-encoded metallo-beta-lactamase (VIM) in gram-negative bacterial clinical isolates from Ouagadougou, Burkina Faso

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ABSTRACT

INTRODUCTION: *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Klebsiella oxytoca* are among the most frequently isolated pathogens implicated in human disease in Burkina Faso. In addition, the emergence of carbapenem-resistant *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *K. oxytoca* due to the production of IMP and VIM enzymes and the spread of these bacteria is a real concern for health facilities. However, the coexistence of the resistance genes encoding these enzymes in clinical bacterial isolates from Burkina Faso has not been previously reported.

OBJECTIVE: To prove the coexistence of VIM and IMP in *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa* and *K. oxytoca* clinical isolates from two medical centers in Ouagadougou, Burkina Faso, by means of conventional PCR.

METHODS: Antibiotic susceptibility testing of 158 gram-negative bacilli isolates was performed against carbapenems and aztreonam using the disk diffusion method. The resistant isolates were screened using conventional polymerase chain reaction for the *bla*_{VIM} and *bla*_{IMP} genes.

RESULTS: *E. coli* (45.1%, 41 isolates) was the most common among the resistant species, with a higher level of resistance to ertapenem (20.9%, 19 isolates) from all the carbapenems. *P. aeruginosa* (9.9%, 9 isolates) and *K. oxytoca* (1.1%, one isolate) were less common resistant species. The genes *bla*_{VIM} and *bla*_{IMP} were detected simultaneously in only 5.5% (5 isolates) of the resistant bacterial strains, including three strains of *E. coli*, one strain of *P. aeruginosa*, and one strain of *K. oxytoca*.

CONCLUSION: This study established the coexistence of *bla*_{VIM} and *bla*_{IMP} genes in *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *K. oxytoca* strains isolated from patients at the Centre Hospitalier Universitaire de Tengandogo and the Hôpital Saint Camille de Ouagadougou in Burkina Faso. These bacterial isolates were resistant to carbapenems due to the production of VIM and IMP enzymes.

Keywords: Carbapenem resistance, coexistence of *bla*_{VIM} and *bla*_{IMP} genes, *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Klebsiella oxytoca*, Burkina Faso

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INTRODUCTION

Over the last decade, antibiotic resistance in bacteria, particularly in gram-negative bacilli (GNB), has become a major public health problem. Among multidrug-resistant GNB, carbapenem-resistant Enterobacterales and *P. aeruginosa* are included in Priority 1 or critical group and Priority 2 or high priority group, respectively, in the WHO Bacterial Priority Pathogens List (2024), requiring an urgent need for the development of new antimicrobials [1]. *E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa* are bacterial species that are frequently isolated and are causative agents of infections in humans. *P. aeruginosa* and *E. coli* are involved in the three main nosocomial infections: catheter-associated urinary tract infections, pneumonia associated with mechanical ventilation, and catheter-associated bloodstream infections, particularly in patients in intensive care units, and in immunocompromised individuals [2-5]. *E. coli* is also known to be a predominant pathogen of urinary tract infections in community settings [6]. *K. oxytoca* is an emerging pathogen of urinary tract infections [7]. It is recognized as an opportunistic and nosocomial pathogen that causes various other infections, such as antibiotic-associated hemorrhagic colitis, pneumonia and other respiratory tract infections, sepsis, bacteremia, skin and soft tissue infections, and intra-abdominal infections [8-9]. Infections caused by carbapenem-resistant *K. oxytoca* are associated with high mortality; hence, these bacteria are considered an emerging public health threat [9]. Therefore, the emergence and spread of carbapenem-resistant *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *K. oxytoca*, which produce IMP and VIM carbapenemases, are a real concern for healthcare facilities worldwide. Indeed, bacteria that produce VIM and IMP, the most important and widespread metallo-beta-lactamases (MBL), represent a growing challenge for clinical care [10, 11]. The VIM and IMP carbapenemases are encoded by *bla*_{VIM} and *bla*_{IMP} resistance genes and are frequently identified in pathogenic GNB, notably *P. aeruginosa*, and several species of enterobacteria including *E. coli* and *K. oxytoca* [10-12]. In these bacteria, *bla*_{VIM} and *bla*_{IMP} genes may be hosted individually, coexist simultaneously, or in association with genes encoding other carbapenemases. The co-expression of VIM and IMP, the subject of our study, has been reported by several research groups from Africa and the Middle East: in *E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa* in Tanzania [13], South Africa [14], and Iran [15], and in *P. aeruginosa* in Egypt [16]. In *K. oxytoca*, *bla*_{VIM} and *bla*_{IMP} have been identified much more often individually or in association with other carbapenem resistance genes, for example in China [9] and Spain [8], but they have rarely been reported to exist simultaneously in the same strain.

In Burkina Faso, in the previous studies the presence of MBL-encoding genes has been reported in clinical GNB isolates that were resistant to carbapenems [17-23]. In the course of these studies, *bla*_{VIM}, *bla*_{IMP}, and *bla*_{NDM} genes were detected in clinical isolates of *E. coli* and/or *K. pneumoniae* resistant to carbapenems and other beta-lactams. However, *bla*_{VIM}, *bla*_{IMP}, and *bla*_{NDM} genes were individually identified in these strains. Only Bambara et al. [23] reported the coexistence of *bla*_{IMP} and *bla*_{NDM} in clinical isolates of *E. coli* and *Klebsiella* spp. in Ouagadougou, Burkina Faso.

To the best of our knowledge, no case of coexistence of *bla*_{VIM} and *bla*_{IMP} genes in *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *K. oxytoca* producing MBL has yet been reported in bacterial isolates from our country. Therefore, this study was carried out with the aim of genotypically detecting the coexistence of genes encoding VIM and IMP enzymes in *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *K. oxytoca* isolates from medical centers in Ouagadougou, Burkina Faso.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Bacterial strains

In this study, we analyzed 186 bacterial samples previously collected from medical centers in Ouagadougou, Burkina Faso, and stored in the Pietro Annigoni Biomolecular Research Center (CERBA)/Molecular Biology and Genetics Laboratory (LABIOGENE) biobank at -20°C or -80°C in Luria Bertani broth supplemented with 30% glycerol. These samples were gram-negative bacilli (GNB) isolates originating from the Centre Hospitalier Universitaire de Tengandogo (CHU-T) and Hôpital Saint Camille de Ouagadougou (HOSCO) in Burkina Faso. CHU-T and HOSCO are among the main university hospitals in Ouagadougou, Burkina Faso. The CHU-T is also the largest modern referral hospital in Burkina Faso. Bacterial samples were collected from September 2018 to October 2018 and from August 2022 to September 2022. The samples were isolated from urine, stool, pus, blood cultures, vaginal and vulvar swabs, and peritoneal fluids collected from outpatients and hospitalized patients. API 20E gallery tests (BioMerieux S. A., France) were used to identify bacterial species. In the framework of our study, which aimed to genotypically detect simultaneous co-production of VIM and IMP carbapenemases in GNB clinical isolates, 158 isolates resistant to third generation cephalosporins were selected for antibiotic resistance testing with carbapenems and/or aztreonam. The resistant isolates were screened using conventional PCR for genes encoding VIM (*bla*_{VIM}) and IMP (*bla*_{IMP}) beta-lactamases. These 158 isolates included 77 *E. coli*,

41 *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, 11 *P. aeruginosa*, 7 *Proteus mirabilis*, 6 *Enterobacter cloacae*, 1 *Enterobacter aerogenes*, 1 *Enterobacter sakazii*, 2 *Citrobacter freundii*, 1 *Citrobacter brakii*, 1 *Citrobacter youngae*, 1 *Acinetobacter baumannii*, 4 *Serratia marcescens*, 1 *Serratia odorifera*, 1 *K. oxytoca*, 2 *Salmonella arizonae*, and 1 *Pseudomonas fluorescens*.

Antimicrobial susceptibility testing

In order to identify carbapenem-resistant isolates, the sensitivity tests of bacterial isolates to imipenem IPM (10 µg), meropenem MRP (10 µg), ertapenem ETP (10 µg), doripenem DOR (10 µg), and aztreonam ATM (30 µg) were performed using the disk diffusion method on Mueller–Hinton (MH) agar medium (Liofilchem, Italy) according to the CA-SFM/EUCAST guidelines [24]. All GNB isolates that showed intermediate susceptibility or resistance to at least one carbapenem and/or aztreonam were considered carbapenem-resistant and subsequently screened for *bla_{VIM}* and *bla_{IMP}* genes.

Molecular detection of co-existence of VIM and IMP genes in bacterial strains

Bacterial isolates resistant to at least one of the antibiotics tested were cultured on MH medium for 24 h at 37°C, using the boiling method [25]. Then DNA from these samples was extracted, quantified using a Nanodrop spectrophotometer (Thermo Scientific, USA), and stored at -20°C or -80°C until use. These DNA samples were screened by conventional PCR using forward and reverse *bla_{VIM}* primers (5'-GTTTGGTTCGCATATCGCAAC-3' and 3'-AATGCGCAGCACCAGGATAG-5') with an amplicon size of 382 bp [26] and *bla_{IMP}* primers (5'-CATGGTTTGGTGGTTCTTGT-3' and 3'-ATAATTTGGCGGACTTTGGC-5') with an amplicon

size of 488 bp [27]. Amplification reactions were carried out in a total of 20 µl reaction mixture (4 µl of 5X Firepol® Master Mix, 0.5 µl of 10 µM forward primer, 0.5 µl of 10 µM reverse primer (concentration of the stock solution of both primers was 100 µM), 14 µl of PCR water, and 1 µl of DNA) using a GeneAmp System PCR 9700 thermal cycler (Applied Biosystems, USA). The cycling protocol consisted of an initial denaturation for 5 min at 96°C, followed by 30 cycles of denaturation at 96°C for 30 s, annealing at 61°C and 54°C for 30 s for *bla_{VIM}* and *bla_{IMP}*, respectively, and extension for 30 s at 72°C. The final extension step was performed at 72°C for 7 min. Finally, the PCR products were analyzed by electrophoretic migration on a 1.5% agarose gel and visualized under ultraviolet light using a Vilber E-Box transilluminator.

Statistical analysis

Sample collection data were entered and processed in Excel 2016 and analyzed using IBM SPSS (Standard Statistical Package for Social Sciences) version 2022. We used the Descriptive Statistics of IBM SPSS software to generate the tables.

RESULTS

Antibiotic resistance profiles of the bacterial strains

Among the 158 GNB isolates tested for antibiotic susceptibility, 91 (57.6%) were resistant to at least one carbapenem and/or aztreonam. Eleven bacterial species were identified among the 91 resistant isolates. Most isolates (74, 81.3%) were from Hôpital Saint Camille de Ouagadougou (HOSCO) and 17 (18.7%) isolates originated from the CHU-T (Fig. 1). *E. coli* and *K. pneumoniae* were the predominant resistant species

Fig. 1. Frequency of resistant bacterial strains from the different collection sites.

reaching 45.1% (41 isolates) and 26.5% (24 isolates) respectively from the total number of isolates (91); followed by *P. aeruginosa* 9.9% (9 isolates), *P. mirabilis* 4.4% (4 isolates), *S. marcescens* 4.4% (4 isolates), *E. cloacae* 3.3% (3 isolates), *C. freundii* 2.2% (2 isolates), *E. aerogenes* 1.1% (1 isolate), *S. odorifera* 1.1% (1 isolate), *K. oxytoca* 1.1% (1 isolate) and *S. arizonae* 1.1% (1 isolate) (Fig. 1).

E. coli isolates mainly came from urine (23.1%, 21 isolate); while *P. aeruginosa* strains were mostly isolated from urine (4.4%, 4 isolates) and pus (4.4%, 4 isolates); and the only *K. oxytoca* resistant strain was isolated from urine (Table 1).

The results of the antibiotic sensitivity test showed that *E. coli* had more resistant strains, with the highest

rates of resistance to aztreonam (41.8%, 38 isolates) and ertapenem (20.9%, 19 isolates) (Fig. 2). All nine strains of *P. aeruginosa* were resistant to aztreonam; however, among carbapenems, the highest resistance rates were observed against imipenem (7.7%, seven isolates) followed by ertapenem (6.6%, six isolates). The only isolate of *K. oxytoca* was resistant to all antibiotics.

Molecular detection of the co-existence of VIM and IMP genes

Molecular screening for *bla*_{VIM} and *bla*_{IMP} genes revealed that only five isolates harbored the two genes *bla*_{VIM} and *bla*_{IMP} simultaneously (Table 2). This coexistence of

Table 1. Frequency of resistant bacteria in samples from different biological specimens and different patients

	Bacterial species, N (%)											Total, N (%)
	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>Proteus mirabilis</i>	<i>Enterobacter cloacae</i>	<i>Enterobacter aerogenes</i>	<i>Citrobacter freundii</i>	<i>Serratia marcescens</i>	<i>Serratia odorifera</i>	<i>K. oxytoca</i>	<i>Salmonella arizonae</i>	
Specimens												
Urine	21 (23.1)	14 (15.4)	4 (4.4)	1 (1.1)	1 (1.1)	0	1 (1.1)	2 (2.2)	1 (1.1)	1 (1.1)	0	46 (50.6)
Stools	12 (13.2)	8 (8.8)	1 (1.1)	3 (3.3)	2 (2.2)	1 (1.1)	1 (1.1)	2 (2.2)	0	0	0	30 (33.0)
Pus	6 (6.6)	1 (1.1)	4 (4.4)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1 (1.1)	12 (13.2)
Blood	1 (1.1)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1 (1.1)
Vaginal swab	1 (1.1)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1 (1.1)
Vulvar swab	0	1 (1.1)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1 (1.1)
Total	41 (45.1)	24 (26.4)	9 (9.9)	4 (4.4)	3 (3.3)	1 (1.1)	2 (2.2)	4 (4.4)	1 (1.1)	1 (1.1)	1 (1.1)	91 (100)
Patient's Sex												
Female	18 (19.8)	14 (15.4)	5 (5.5)	4 (4.4)	0	0	2 (2.2)	2 (2.2)	0	1 (1.1)	1 (1.1)	47 (51.6)
Male	17 (18.7)	6 (6.6)	4 (4.4)	0	3 (3.3)	0	0	1 (1.1)	1 (1.1)	0	0	32 (35.2)
Not known	6 (6.6)	4 (4.4)	0	0	0	1 (1.1)	0	1 (1.1)	0	0	0	12 (13.2)
Total	41 (45.1)	24 (26.4)	9 (9.9)	4 (4.4)	3 (3.3)	1 (1.1)	2 (2.2)	4 (4.4)	1 (1.1)	1 (1.1)	1 (1.1)	91 (100)
Hospitalization												
Yes	25 (27.5)	15 (16.5)	5 (5.5)	4 (4.4)	2 (2.2)	0	1 (1.1)	1 (1.1)	1 (1.1)	1 (1.1)	0	55 (60.4)
No	9 (9.9)	6 (6.6)	4 (4.4)	0	1 (1.1)	1 (1.1)	1 (1.1)	2 (2.2)	0	0	0	24 (26.4)
Not known	7 (7.7)	3 (3.3)	0	0	0	0	0	1 (1.1)	0	0	1 (1.1)	12 (13.2)
Total	41 (45.1)	24 (26.4)	9 (9.9)	4 (4.4)	3 (3.3)	1 (1.1)	2 (2.2)	4 (4.4)	1 (1.1)	1 (1.1)	1 (1.1)	91 (100)

the two genes is indicated in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4 showing electrophoresis bands of approximately 488 bp for *bla*_{IMP} and 382 bp for *bla*_{VIM} from the same bacterial strain. Of these five isolates, three were *E. coli*, one was *P. aeruginosa*, and one was *K. oxytoca* (Table 2). All the three *E. coli* strains were resistant to ertapenem, the *K. oxytoca* strain

was resistant to all carbapenems and aztreonam, and the *P. aeruginosa* strain was resistant to imipenem and aztreonam (Table 3). Three of the five strains harboring VIM- and IMP-producing genes were isolated from urine samples, and two from pus. Four of these strains were isolated from hospitalized patients (Table 3).

Table 2. Prevalence of coexistence of VIM and IMP genes in *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *K. oxytoca*

Bacterial species	Simultaneous presence of VIM and IMP genes, N (%)	VIM gene only, N	IMP gene only, N (%)
<i>E. coli</i>	3 (60.0)	0	14 (87.5)
<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	1 (20.0)	0	2 (12.5)
<i>K. oxytoca</i>	1 (20.0)	0	0 (0.0)
Total	5 (100)	0	16 (100)

N – number of strains of certain bacterial species coharboring the two resistance genes or harboring one resistant gene

Fig. 2. Resistance rate of bacterial strains to different antibiotics.

Fig 3. Electrophoresis gel results. Identification of *bla*_{IMP} gene in PCR products of genetic material from *K. oxytoca* strain (8CHT) positive for the *bla*_{IMP} gene. M – DNA ladder molecular weight marker (Solis Biodyne, Estonia) (100 bp); T – negative control.

Fig. 4. Electrophoresis gel results. Identification of bla_{VIM} gene in PCR products of genetic material from *K. oxytoca* strain (number 8 = 8CHT) positive for the bla_{VIM} gene. Numbers 2, 4, 5, ... ,33 represent bacterial strains samples: 2CHT, 4CHT, 5CHT, ..., 33CHT, correspondingly; CHT – indicates bacterial isolate collected from CHU-T; M – DNA ladder molecular weight marker (Solis Biodyne, Estonia) (100 bp); TN – negative control; 8 = 8CHT – *K. oxytoca* strain positive for the bla_{VIM} gene.

Table 3. Antibiotic resistance profile of bacteria coharboring the two resistance genes and their distribution in different biological specimens and among different patients

Characteristics	Bacterial species, N (%)			Total, N (%)
	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>K. oxytoca</i>	
Coexistence of bla_{VIM} and bla_{IMP} genes	3 (60.0)	1(20.0)	1(20.0)	5 (100)
Antibiotic resistance				
IPM	1 (20.0)	1 (20.0)	1 (20.0)	3 (60.0)
MRP	1 (20.0)	0	1 (20.0)	2 (40.0)
ETP	3 (60.0)	0	1 (20.0)	4 (80.0)
DOR	1 (20.0)	0	1 (20.0)	2 (40.0)
ATM	2 (40.0)	1 (20.0)	1 (20.0)	4 (80.0)
Specimens				
Urine	2 (40.0)	0	1 (20.0)	3 (60.0)
Pus	1 (20.0)	1 (20.0)	0	2 (40.0)
Total	3 (60.0)	1 (20.0)	1 (20.0)	5 (100)
Patient's Sex				
Female	2 (40.0)	0	1 (20.0)	3 (60.0)
Male	1 (20.0)	1 (20.0)	0	2 (40.0)
Total cases	3 (60.0)	1 (20.0)	1 (20.0)	5 (100)
Hospitalization				
Yes	2 (40.0)	1 (20.0)	1 (20.0)	4 (80.0)
No	1 (20.0)	0	0	1 (20.0)
Total cases	3 (60.0)	1 (20.0)	1 (20.0)	5 (100)

N – number of strains of certain bacterial species coharboring the two resistance genes; IPM – imipenem, MRP – meropenem, ETP – ertapenem, DOR – doripenem, ATM – aztreonam

DISCUSSION

The results of antibiotic susceptibility testing showed that *E. coli* was the most prevalent resistant species (45.1%) of all tested bacterial isolates, whereas *P. aeruginosa* and *K. oxytoca* were among the minority species, corresponding to 9.9% and 1.1% of all tested bacterial isolates, respectively (Fig. 1). Owusu et al. [28] found that *E. coli* was the most prevalent resistant species in Ghana, with a prevalence of 46.0% (n=83), followed by *P. aeruginosa* at 4.4% (n=8), while *K. oxytoca* was the least prevalent, at 0.6% (n=1). Similar results were also reported in Burkina Faso by Kabore et al. [19], with a higher frequency of resistant isolates for *E. coli* (82.7%) than for *P. aeruginosa*, with a prevalence of only 1.9%. In addition, the resistant strains in our study were frequently isolated from the urine: 50.6% (n=46), including 23.1% (n=21) *E. coli* strains, 4.4% (n=4) *P. aeruginosa* strains, and 1.1% (n=1) *K. oxytoca* strains (Table 1). The prevalence of *E. coli* among resistant strains could be explained by the predominance of urine samples and the fact that *E. coli* is known to be the bacterial species most involved in urinary tract infections [6].

With regard to carbapenem sensitivity profiles, our results were similar to those of Owusu et al. [28] from Ghana, who found that *E. coli* strains had the highest level of resistance to ertapenem (22% from total 83 isolates) compared with 20.9% (from total 91 isolates) in our study; the only *K. oxytoca* strain was also resistant to ertapenem. In contrast, Bambara et al. [23], in another study carried out in Burkina Faso, found very high levels of resistance to ertapenem, meropenem, imipenem, and doripenem in pathogenic GNB, with rates of 64.0%, 41.0%, 53.0%, and 73.0%, respectively, compared to 22.0% for imipenem, meropenem, and doripenem and 44.0% for ertapenem obtained in our study. Although in our study *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *K. oxytoca* strains were more resistant to ertapenem among the other carbapenems at 20.9%, 6.6%, and 1.1% level, respectively, these resistance rates were lower compared to 67.0%, 43.0%, and 62.0%, respectively, for the same bacterial strains reported by Bambara et al. [23]. The authors of a SENTRY study carried out in China found that the resistance rates of *K. oxytoca* to imipenem and ertapenem were 1.1% and 1.8%, respectively [29]. The low rates of bacterial resistance to carbapenems in our study can be explained by the fact that carbapenems are still the most effective antibiotics used as a last resort for the treatment of infections caused by the multi-resistant bacteria. However, we may have underestimated the rate of bacterial resistance because we used the disc diffusion method in our experiments. This phenotypic method is based on antibiotic susceptibility testing, and it is not

always easy to demonstrate resistance to carbapenems using this method [20]. The different sample sizes and geographical variation in the distribution of resistant strains could also be significant factors contributing to the variations in results from different studies. VIM, IMP, and NDM enzymes are the most widespread metallo-beta-lactamases detected in bacteria worldwide. They are encoded by *bla*_{VIM}, *bla*_{IMP}, and *bla*_{NDM} genes, respectively, which are the most prevalent MBL genes in bacteria widespread on several continents, including Africa, Asia, Europe, and the Americas [30]. These resistance genes are carried by mobile genetic elements (plasmids) that are compatible with a wide range of pathogens of clinical interest [31]. According to reports from different countries the *bla*_{VIM} and *bla*_{IMP} genes are frequently identified in pathogenic GNB, notably *P. aeruginosa* and several species of Enterobacteriaceae, including *E. coli* and *K. oxytoca* [10-12, 32]. In these bacteria, *bla*_{VIM} and *bla*_{IMP} genes may be hosted individually or coexist simultaneously or in association with genes encoding other carbapenemases. The coexistence of two or more MBL genes in bacteria or their coexistence with other resistance genes, including *bla*_{KPC}, significantly reduces the sensitivity of bacterial strains to β -lactam antibiotics [30], thereby increasing their level of resistance [33]. This finding is consistent with the carbapenem resistance profile of *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *K. oxytoca* cohosting *bla*_{VIM} and *bla*_{IMP} that showed relatively high rates of resistance to carbapenems in our experiments (Table 3). In our study, molecular analysis using conventional PCR targeting the *bla*_{VIM} and *bla*_{IMP} genes in strains resistant to at least one of the carbapenems and/or aztreonam revealed the coexistence of the two MBL genes in five (5.5%) isolates, including three *E. coli*, one *P. aeruginosa*, and one *K. oxytoca*. In numerous studies, several carbapenemase genes encoding VIM, IMP, NDM, KPC and OXA-48 have been detected either alone or in coexistence in multidrug-resistant clinical isolates of *P. aeruginosa* and Enterobacteriaceae species including *E. coli*, *K. pneumoniae*, and *K. oxytoca* [8, 9, 13-16, 34]. A prevalence of 6.6% (15 isolates) of carbapenem-resistant GNB clinical isolates harboring more than one carbapenemase-encoding gene was reported by Mushi et al. [13] in Tanzania, which is similar to the results of our study (5.5%, 5 isolates). This Tanzanian study showed the coexistence of *bla*_{VIM} and *bla*_{IMP} genes in strains of *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *K. pneumoniae* resistant to ertapenem and/or meropenem. A study conducted in Egypt showed the co-production of VIM and IMP enzymes in four (28.6%) clinical strains of imipenem-resistant *P. aeruginosa* [16]. Our results are similar to those of Armin et al. [15] from Iran, who found that four strains

of carbapenem-resistant Enterobacteriaceae, including *E. coli*, harbored both bla_{VIM} and bla_{IMP} genes. Similarly, in 2018 study from Sudan, Adam et Elhag [35] reported that bla_{VIM} and bla_{IMP} genes were co-expressed in the same strains of *E. coli* (2 isolates) and *P. aeruginosa* (1 isolate) and that in addition, three genes bla_{VIM} , bla_{IMP} and bla_{NDM} coexisted in one strain of *E. coli*, one of *P. aeruginosa* and one of *Proteus vulgaris*. In a study from Burkina Faso Bambara et al. [23] observed the coexistence of bla_{IMP} and bla_{NDM} in 5 bacterial strains (6.7%), including two *E. coli* isolates and three *Klebsiella* spp. Scientific publications worldwide have reported several cases of carbapenem resistance in *E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa* through the coproduction of VIM and IMP enzymes. Cases of the coexistence of only two MBL-encoding genes, bla_{IMP} and bla_{VIM} , in carbapenem-resistant *K. oxytoca* have rarely been reported. In our study, both MBL genes were detected simultaneously in only one *K. oxytoca* isolate, which was resistant to all carbapenems. However, researchers from other countries have usually reported cases of coexistence of carbapenemase genes that encode VIM or IMP enzymes with those encoding NDM or KPC-type enzymes in *K. oxytoca* [29, 36]. In contrast to our study, other authors from Burkina Faso reported an 11.7% prevalence of imipenem-resistant *K. oxytoca* with a single bla_{VIM} gene [21]. IMP- and NDM-encoding genes have also been detected in *K. oxytoca* strains from Europe [8, 29], Egypt [37], and China [9]. Co-expression of carbapenemase genes, particularly those encoding MBL, can be explained by the fact that plasmids carry several of these resistance genes.

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The results of our study and studies on carbapenem resistance previously carried out in our country emphasize that GNB containing the carbapenemase genes bla_{VIM} , bla_{IMP} , bla_{NDM} , bla_{KPC} , and bla_{OXA-48} circulate in hospital and community settings in Burkina Faso. To the best of our knowledge, our study is the first of its kind in Burkina Faso to report the coexistence of the bla_{VIM} and bla_{IMP} genes in the same clinical isolates of *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *K. oxytoca*.

CONCLUSION

In the context of antimicrobial resistance, carbapenem-resistant MBL-producing GNB have become a new threat to public health in Burkina Faso and worldwide. In this study we reported cases of coexistence of bla_{VIM} and bla_{IMP} genes in carbapenem-resistant clinical isolates of *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *K. oxytoca* collected from the Centre Hospitalier Universitaire de Tengandogo (CHU-T) and Hôpital Saint Camille de Ouagadougou (HOSCO) in Burkina Faso. This highlights the problem that our healthcare system currently faces, namely, the resistance of bacteria to β -lactam antibiotics mediated by the production of carbapenemases. Resistance to carbapenem antibiotics not only limits the therapeutic options available for treating infections but also leads to therapeutic impasses, increasing healthcare costs and mortality. Consequently, a national epidemiological surveillance system incorporating the "One Health" approach is required to prevent and control the spread of carbapenem-resistant bacteria in Burkina Faso.

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